

Online Obstacle Avoidance in Teach-and-Repeat Navigation

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Abstract—Teach-and-repeat navigation is a simple approach that allows mobile robots to learn a desired path. It can offer practical advantages over a full navigation stack when the robot needs to perform repetitive tasks. There are several approaches to teach-and-repeat navigation in the literature. They usually involve showing a desired path to the robot to make it repeat it robustly, starting from different points than the initial one. However, they do not deal with unforeseen obstacles that may appear along the path after the teach phase. In this work, we propose an alternative strategy for teach-and-repeat navigation to handle these unexpected situations. Our approach combines the Dynamic Movement Primitives, which are employed to encode the desired route for the robot, with the Artificial Potentials Fields method for the obstacle avoidance part. The method was validated in a simulated environment using a mobile robot with a 2-D laser scanner. Preliminary results seem to confirm the effectiveness of this approach in the context of teach-and-repeat navigation. Indeed, the robot can correctly avoid the obstacle, returning to the predefined path afterward.

I. INTRODUCTION

The field of mobile robotics has made significant progress in recent years. Mobile robots can navigate dynamic and unstructured environments, collaborating with humans and other robots in various domains. Their applications range from simple tasks, i.e., vacuuming floors in households or moving goods or products across a warehouse, to complex missions, i.e., search and rescue operations or exploring unknown or hazardous environments. In some cases, such as when the robot only needs to perform repetitive tasks (e.g., item delivery or infrastructure inspection) or move through a limited area of the environment, it may be convenient to teach the robot a single path that it can repeat multiple times, rather than building the map of the whole environment. This is the idea behind the teach-and-repeat navigation approach ([1–3]). This approach uses two phases to teach mobile robots a path to follow. In the teach phase, the user controls the robot along the desired path while it collects data from the environment. In the repeat phase, the robot uses the recorded information to follow the previously taught path, starting from different points than the initial one. It can use odometry data combined with a single monocular camera ([2, 3]) or a 2-D laser scanner ([1]) to localize itself relative to the previously taught path. The main drawback of the teach-and-repeat approach is that it usually does not consider the presence of unforeseen obstacles that may appear along the desired path after the teach phase. However, if the robot has to repeat the demonstrated route multiple times, this situation may occur at any moment.

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Therefore, it may be convenient to provide a strategy to avoid obstacles while trying to reach the goal in order to prevent the robot from stopping or being shown the desired path again.

In this work, we propose a solution to handle unforeseen obstacles in the context of teach-and-repeat approaches. In particular, our strategy allows the robot to avoid obstacles that appear along the path during the repeat phase, even if they were not present during the teach phase. As a result, the robot can complete the assigned task (i.e., move toward the desired destination) without interruptions, thus providing a more flexible strategy to deal with unforeseen situations.

II. METHOD

We consider an unknown environment and a mobile base equipped with a 2-D laser scanner. The mobile robot is programmed to execute a navigation task (i.e., move from a *start* to an *end* point) through teach-and-repeat navigation. During the teach phase, the user directly controls it in teleoperation. At the beginning of the path demonstration, the robot acquires and stores the point cloud of the environment and starts recording its pose (2-D position and orientation). When the user finishes the demonstration, it stops the recording and saves the new point cloud of the environment. It is possible to repeat this operation several times to teach the robot a longer route.

At the end of the teach phase, the robot has to learn the newly taught navigation task. To this end, a modified version of the Dynamic Movement Primitives (DMPs) [4] is employed. A discrete DMP encodes a point-to-point movement into a mass-spring-damper system perturbed by an external forcing term, allowing it to be generalized and adapted to new start and goal positions. In their standard definition, DMPs do not address the obstacle avoidance problem. However, in [5], the authors propose to add a repulsive term to the original DMPs’ transformation system:

$$\begin{aligned}\tau\dot{\mathbf{v}} &= \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_g - \mathbf{x}) - \mathbf{D}\mathbf{v} - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{x}_g - \mathbf{x}_s)s + \mathbf{K}\mathbf{f}(s) \\ &\quad + \mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) \\ \tau\dot{\mathbf{x}} &= \mathbf{v},\end{aligned}\tag{1}$$

where \mathbf{K} and \mathbf{D} are positive definite matrices that represent the spring and the damping terms, respectively, while the vectors \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{v} are the position and velocity of the system, \mathbf{x}_s and \mathbf{x}_g are the start and goal position, τ is a temporal scaling factor used to modulate the movement duration, and $\mathbf{f}(s)$ is the vector containing the external forcing terms. They choose the repulsive term as the negative gradient of a potential field, i.e., $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v}) = -\nabla U(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})$, which depends on the end-effector’s position \mathbf{x} and velocity \mathbf{v} . In this way, they allow a manipulator to avoid static and moving obstacles. However, they only deal with single-point obstacles.

We employ the same transformation system and choose the repulsive term as the negative gradient of a different potential field, essentially combining the Artificial Potential Fields (APFs) method with DMPs, also taking into account the possibility of avoiding complex obstacles. Indeed, we consider the following repulsive potential

$$U(\mathbf{x}) = \begin{cases} \frac{k}{\gamma} \left(\frac{1}{\rho(\mathbf{x})} - \frac{1}{\rho_0} \right)^\gamma & \text{if } \rho(\mathbf{x}) \leq \rho_0 \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases},$$

in which ρ_0 is the radius of influence of the obstacle, k is a constant gain and γ is typically chosen equal to 2. The term $\rho(\mathbf{x})$ is the distance of \mathbf{x} from a complex obstacle \mathcal{O} :

$$\rho(\mathbf{x}) = \min_{\mathbf{x}' \in \mathcal{O}} \|\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{x}'\|.$$

During the repeat phase, the robot first must determine its current position relative to the *teach* path (i.e., the one demonstrated to the robot). For this purpose, it acquires the point cloud of the scene and compares it to the one stored in the teach phase, using the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm. This process is fundamental because the robot may start the navigation task from a slightly different point than the initial one of the *teach* path. The reference path is then computed through the DMPs, selecting the robot's current position as the initial position \mathbf{x}_s and the last point of the learned route as the goal \mathbf{x}_g . At this point, the robot can follow the generated path until it reaches the desired destination. When an obstacle appears along the learned path, the repulsive term $\mathbf{p}(\mathbf{x}, \mathbf{v})$ in the transformation system (1) causes the DMPs to modify the movement they generate according to the properties of the potential function. Since DMPs use a set of equations with attractor dynamics to represent movements, these are robust to perturbations (i.e., the repulsive force surrounding the obstacle). In this way, the robot has as a reference a new movement that allows it to avoid the obstacle while remaining attracted to the original demonstrated movement. Consequently, after circumventing the obstacle, it can return to the *teach* path and reach the desired destination.

III. EXPERIMENTS

We tested this method in a simulated environment running on a DELL G15 equipped with a 10th-generation Intel i7 processor and a NVIDIA GeForce RTX 3060 GPU. The simulator we chose is Gazebo 9 interfaced with ROS Melodic. The simulated system used for the experiments is the Summit XL Steel.

During the teach phase, a user drove the mobile base from the Start point to the End point in a simulated environment (Fig. 1) using the keyboard. At these points, the robot acquired the point cloud of the environment and recorded its odometry data. In this phase, there were no obstacles on the path. The *teach* path was then learned by employing the DMPs. In the repeat phase, we decided to verify first if the robot had learned the navigation task correctly (i.e., if it could follow the learned path robustly) without introducing any obstacles on the *teach* path (Fig. 1a). As shown in Fig. 2a, the robot can reproduce it perfectly. Then, we inserted a box close to the path (Fig. 1b), whose position was known a priori. Fig. 2b exhibits the result

(a) No obstacles on the *teach* path (b) Obstacle on the *teach* path

Figure 1: Simulated environment used for the experiments

(a) No obstacles on the *teach* path (b) Obstacle on the *teach* path

Figure 2: Robot's *teach* and *repeat* paths

in this case: the robot successfully avoids the obstacle and then returns to the desired path, reaching the goal correctly.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this work, we proposed a strategy for obstacle avoidance in teach-and-repeat navigation. Simulative results confirmed that it is possible to rely on DMPs to encode the desired route for the robot and combine them with APFs to deal with unforeseen obstacles. In particular, we showed that the robot could reproduce the navigation task correctly, avoiding obstacles and returning to the learned path to reach its goal. However, some aspects need to be improved: indeed, we supposed we knew the position of the obstacle. In future work, we should consider an obstacle detection technique. Moreover, the APFs method suffers from some drawbacks (e.g., being trapped in a local minimum region or unable to reach goals with obstacles nearby), so a solution to these problems should be found. Nevertheless, our approach offers a suitable solution to deal with unexpected obstacles in teach-and-repeat navigation since it prevents the robot from stopping or being shown the desired path again, improving its navigation.

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